

Thinking Fast - A Bionic Approach to Soft Computing

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Abstract. Evolution has enabled living organisms to respond to sensory input very fast in order to safeguard their chances of survival. This ability is largely based on the classification of perceptions into categories and their collective processing in associative structures. These associative structures, in turn, have a remarkable similarity to the biological neural networks which perform them. The author has chosen this natural way of *thinking fast* as a model for an innovative bionic approach to soft computing.

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1 Introduction

Readers who are acquainted with prospect theory in economics will notice that the title of this paper alludes to the 2011 book “*Thinking, Fast and Slow*” by psychologist Daniel Kahneman, who was awarded the 2002 Nobel Memorial Prize in Economic Sciences (shared with Vernon L. Smith) (Kahneman, 2013). The book’s main thesis is that of explaining human cognition and formation of judgement based on two modes of thought:

“*System 1*” represents the unconscious and innate ability of the human brain to instinctively categorize any type of perception by automatically associating it with vital emotional reactions (e.g. fear) and memorized experiences. It is fast because the biological neural network takes advantage of parallelly processing sensory impressions.

On the other hand, “*System 2*” stands for the intellectual post-processing of emotions and memories being elicited by system 1 and offered to our consciousness for deliberate mental verification before responding to the perception with an adequate action or decision. Compared to system 1, system 2 works slowly due to the serial mode of operations when our mind is drawing conclusions.

Daniel Kahneman and his scientific colleague Amos Tversky, who already passed away in 1996, were mainly interested in explaining why human decision-making is inconsistent with that of perfectly rational agents. This paper, on the other hand, assumes a bionic point of view on the principles of operation which evolution has assigned to system 1 and describes how they can be exploited for a new approach to soft computing.

2 The architecture of system 1

In 1972, the Dutch computer scientist Gerrit Blaauw defined the notion of *system architecture* as follows (Blaauw, 1972):

“The architecture of a system can be defined as the functional appearance of the system to the user, its phenomenology.”

This means that the following explanations will be confined to the functions which make up the essence of system 1 and which are of fundamental importance for the pursued bionic approach. Therefore, the paper will not deal with the physiological details of system 1, which may either belong to the *system implementation* that performs the architecture (i.e. the logical design), or to the *system realization* that embodies the implementation.

Considering the beginning of evolutionary development, it becomes apparent that even the first life forms had two elementary abilities:

1. sensory perception
2. categorization

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According to the current state of research, we know that already about 3.5 billion years ago, the single-cell organisms that came into existence at hot springs in the depth of primeval oceans featured chemoreceptors as sense organs in order to satisfy their vital energy requirements (Wehrmann, 2013). Using them, these bacterium-like creatures were able to perceive substances suitable for nutrition (e.g. sugar or amino acids) and to distinguish them from toxic chemicals (e.g. heavy metals), thus *categorizing* information about their hostile environment. The classification of sensory input into categories, like “nourishing” and “poisonous” or “dangerous” and “harmless”, makes it possible to simplify or rather abstract from the environmental complexity.

The aspect of information filtering gains particular significance with the emergence of the first eyes about 540 million years ago (Pfaff, 2002). With the possibility of distinguishing between more than light and dark, the amount of received information increases more and more. The reduction of sensory impressions to categories ensures that the gradually emerging higher cognitive abilities of further developed life forms do not overcharge the respective demand for energy.

At the same time, one can assume that the category is equal to the origin of language development by structuring the sensations into thoughts (terms) and by storing (remembering) them in the neural network in order to have them available for subsequent treatment (i.e. deriving other thoughts or evoking actions).

The next step to communication with fellow species or with other life forms already occurs at that moment in time when living beings become able to pass on cognitively conceived categories to others by expressing their perceptions or intentions using sounds (i.e. warning cries) or body language (i.e. threatening gestures or courtship behavior).

Incidentally, these considerations are just as applicable to plants, after botanical scientists have discovered that these organisms also have sensory and even communication capabilities (Weber, 2015), (Mancuso & Viola, 2015).

It is well-known that the evolution of life is based on a natural optimization process which consists of the cyclically repeated sequence of reproduction, mutation and selection. Another natural optimizing principle appears in the tendency of dynamic systems to assume an equilibrium state at a lower level of energy.

An illustrative example of the second principle can be found in the paper “*Collective Computation in Neuronlike Circuits*” by David W. Tank and John J. Hopfield (Tank & Hopfield, 1987). The authors report that electronic circuits based on neurobiological models can solve complex problems rapidly. For instance, they show that it is possible to find optimal solutions for the combinatorial *assignment problem* well-known in operations research by means of collective interaction of operational amplifiers replacing the neurons, while wires, resistors and capacitors replace the synaptic connections. In their paper, Tank and Hopfield emphasize that their special interest in such types of artificial “neural circuits” concerns the possibility of understanding perceptive cognition as a series of optimization problems. Even then, the experiments studied by Tank and Hopfield reveal a general principle underlying the cognitive abilities of system 1 (Grottrian, 1988), (Schmidt, 1989). It can be characterized by the following phenomena observable within the neuron-like circuit solution of the assignment problem described in the paper:

1. The network-like interrelations between the competing decision alternatives of the assignment problem bear a striking resemblance to a physical neural network.
2. The optimal solution of the assignment problem is automatically found inside of an “*energy terrain*”-called basin of attraction.
3. There is no need for a mechanism like a search algorithm that an operations research method would apply to this task.

As even small children, who do not yet have rational thinking at their disposal due to their level of development, can successfully solve an optimization problem by choosing from several offered stimuli (e.g. toys) in order to focus their attention on one of them, the first phenomenon raises the following question:

Does the process of weighing up decision alternatives, which typically shows fluent transitions of thoughts and emotions, only happen to have a structural similarity with the physical neural network that performs the process, or does this similarity suggest the reuse of an evolutionary recipe for success? Does it possibly reveal an underestimated cognitive competence, since the apparently aimless being torn between available alternatives tends to be interpreted as mentally deficient, due to our cultural conditioning which demands of us the ability to reason rationally within a more and more complicated world?

The second phenomenon delivers the explanatory model of why it is easy for us to decide or act spontaneously with often satisfactory outcome, if we just follow the gradient of our preferences.

The third phenomenon means that the feedback connections between the operational amplifiers that belong to the electronic circuit described by Tank and Hopfield represent the properties of an “admissible solution” of the assignment problem expressible by empirical rules. It is remarkable that neither an explicit objective function nor an optimality criterion of the solution must be considered.

Sensory impressions classified by system 1 as categories experience states of activation or inhibition just like biological nerve cells during their subsequent mental treatment, and, after passing through an optimization process, finally approach a consistent system state, which for instance sets off a spontaneous action or retrieves an association that is appropriate to the perception from our memory.

In the following, the imitation of such an evolution-driven functional appearance of system 1 will be the subject of a formal and computer-aided language called *empirical logic* (abbr. EL), which has been prototypically realized using the programmable computer algebra system Maple (Bronstein, et al., 2005, 2006, p. 998 ff).

3 Empirical Logic: Fundamentals of a formal language for computer-aided decision-making with knowledge gained from experience

At this point, some readers may object that the term *empirical logic* is an oxymoron, because conclusions drawn from experience only cannot claim to be logical. Thus, the proof of the Pythagorean theorem would be a matter of logic, but not the reasoning of a doctor who infers a disease from existing symptoms. This opinion, already shared by Rudolf Carnap and others (Carnap, 1968, p. 16) (Böhme, 1981, p. 66), is understandable due to the tremendous progress of formalization of logic since the middle of the 19th century, on the way to the current state of mathematical definition. On account of its success, mathematical logic has become, so to speak, a generic concept, like “to google” for all kind of searching in the Internet. In the end, the classical Greek word “logos” was originally used with the unspecific meaning of “word” or “speech”. Therefore, it is reasonable not to question the doctor's ability to think logically and to be allowed to name this type of thinking *empirical logic*.

The EL notion of a category

To a certain degree, the EL notion *category* resembles the notion of a fuzzy set. Nonetheless, this term will deliberately not be used, because fuzzy logic has sought to extend the concepts of mathematical logic, which empirical logic explicitly does not.

The degree of membership of a given fact to a category is called *validity* and can be measured on a sliding scale either between -1 and +1 or between 0 and +1. The validity values $v \in \mathbb{V} \subset \mathbb{R}$ have the following meanings:

$\mathbb{V} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{array}{ c c } \hline [-1, 1] & [0, 1] \\ \hline \end{array}$		Meaning:
1	1	The fact belongs to this category.
0.5	0.75	The fact mainly belongs to this category.
0	0.5	It is impossible to judge whether the fact belongs to this category.
-0.5	0.25	The fact mainly does not belong to this category.
-1	0	The fact does not belong to this category.

Intermediate validity values between the above listed ones approach their meaning in a sliding mode to that of their respective neighbors.

The available validity expressions $e_TRUE()$, $e_UNKNOWN()$ and $e_FALSE()$ support the correct interpretation of both validity intervals. They can be used in place of the numeric validity values:

Validity expression	$\mathbb{V} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{array}{ c c } \hline [-1, 1] & [0, 1] \\ \hline \end{array}$	
	$[-1, 1]$	$[0, 1]$
$e_TRUE()$	1	1
$e_UNKNOWN()$	0	0.5
$e_FALSE()$	-1	0

This allows us to specify the validity interval as $\mathbb{V} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [e_FALSE(), e_TRUE()] \subset \mathbb{R}$ with the subsets $\mathbb{V}_+ \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (e_UNKNOWN(), e_TRUE())$ and $\mathbb{V}_- \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [e_FALSE(), e_UNKNOWN())$ such that $\mathbb{V} = \mathbb{V}_+ \cup \mathbb{V}_-$.

Here we have some examples of categories:

- Sizes: very small, small, standard size, tall, very tall
- Ages: very young, young, mature, old, very old
- Political opinions: conservative, liberal, right-wing extremist, etc.
- Colors: red, green, yellow, blue, etc.

In principle, there are two types of categories:

Bound categories are bound to a scalable reference magnitude (e.g. sizes, ages, degree of capacity utilization, ...)

Free categories are not bound to a scalable reference magnitude (e.g. political opinions, colors, fashion trends, decisions about task assignments, ...)

Sometimes, you may turn free categories into bound categories if they fit into an ordinal scale. Different from free categories, bound categories can be mathematically described by a *validity function*. The latter is expected to be continuously differentiable, such that a sliding change between different degrees of category membership can be ensured.

Validity functions for bound categories

Fig. 1: Threshold function

Fig. 2: Limitation function

Fig. 3: Interval function

Fig. 4: Estimation function

Considering the parsimony design principle (Blaauw, 1972), the architecture of empirical logic has been confined to exactly four standardized validity functions for bound categories (Fig. 1 to Fig. 4):

1. *Threshold function* ($e_THRESHOLD$)
2. *Limitation function* ($e_LIMITATION$)
3. *Interval function* ($e_INTERVAL$)
4. *Estimation function* ($e_ESTIMATION$)

Parameters allow for adjusting these functions to the characteristics of the respective categories. Moreover, for each of the validity functions, there is an inverse validity function that allows us to derive a concrete value of the reference magnitude from a given validity value of the bound category notion. The available inverse validity functions $e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE$, $e_LIMITATION_INVERSE$, $e_INTERVAL_INVERSE$ and $e_ESTIMATION_INVERSE$ have turned out to be very useful for control engineering applications.

The estimation function $e_ESTIMATION$ (example)

The architecture of the *estimation function* is defined by a strictly increasing and, after reaching an *estimated value*, strictly decreasing bell-shaped curve. It describes a category bound to a reference magnitude whose range of validity values constitutes an interval with the midpoint given by the estimated value (e.g. average machine capacity utilization). The syntax of the estimation function $e_ESTIMATION_{[a,f]}: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$ with the parameters $a \in \mathbb{R}$ and $f \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is

$$e_ESTIMATION(x, a, f)$$

The arguments have the following meaning:

- x : *Reference magnitude* which binds the category.
- a : *Estimated value* of the reference magnitude where the validity of the category assumes the maximum value $e_TRUE()$, such that $e_ESTIMATION(a, a, f) = e_TRUE()$.

f : *Fuzziness* of the category which in case of $\mathbb{V} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} [-1, 1]$ denotes the distance of the zero-crossing points of the estimation function, such that

$$e_ESTIMATION\left(a - \frac{f}{2}, a, f\right) = e_ESTIMATION\left(a + \frac{f}{2}, a, f\right) = e_UNKNOWN()$$

Above and below the estimated value a , the function approaches its limitation value $e_FALSE()$:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \pm\infty} e_ESTIMATION(x, a, f) = e_FALSE()$$

You are free to choose an appropriate implementation of the estimation function within the bounds of the above architectural specification. The already mentioned bell-shaped curve suggests using the Gaussian function. Considering the respective validity intervals, the estimation function then becomes:

$$e_ESTIMATION_{[-1, 1]}(x, a, f) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 2e^{-l(2)\left(\frac{x-a}{f}\right)^2} - 1$$

$$e_ESTIMATION_{[0, 1]}(x, a, f) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e^{-\ln(2)\left(\frac{x-a}{f}\right)^2}$$

The inverse estimation function $e_ESTIMATION_INVERSE$ (example)

Just like the interval function $e_INTERVAL$ the estimation function does not have a closed inverse function. Nevertheless, the function is invertible in sections because of its strict monotonicity below and above its global maximum a . The *inverse estimation function* $e_ESTIMATION_INVERSE_{[z, x_MIN, x_MAX, a, f]}: \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with the parameters $z \in \mathbb{R}$, $x_MIN \in \mathbb{R}$, $x_MAX \in \mathbb{R}$, $a \in \mathbb{R}$ and $f \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ has the following syntax:

$$e_ESTIMATION_INVERSE(v, z, x_MIN, x_MAX, a, f)$$

The arguments have this meaning:

- v : *Validity value* taken from validity interval \mathbb{V} .
- z : Last determined value of the reference magnitude, which is taken as a criterion to decide on the applicable inversion section.
- x_MIN : Minimum permitted value of the reference magnitude.
- x_MAX : Maximum permitted value of the reference magnitude.
- a : *Estimated value* of the reference magnitude.
- f : *Fuzziness* of the category.

Based on the usage of the Gaussian function, you may derive the corresponding implementations of the inverse estimation function for both validity intervals $[-1, 1]$ and $[0, 1]$, as follows:

$$e_ESTIMATION_INVERSE_{[-1, 1]}(v, z, x_MIN, x_MAX, a, f) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} \text{With } x = a - \frac{f}{2} \sqrt{\frac{-\ln\left(\frac{v+1}{2}\right)}{\ln(2)}} \text{ for } z \leq a \\ \text{and } x = a + \frac{f}{2} \sqrt{\frac{-\ln\left(\frac{v+1}{2}\right)}{\ln(2)}} \text{ for } z > a \\ x \quad \text{for } x_MIN \leq x \leq x_MAX \\ x_MIN \text{ for } x < x_MIN \\ x_MAX \text{ for } x > x_MAX \end{cases}$$

$$e_ESTIMATION_INVERSE_{[0, 1]}(v, z, x_MIN, x_MAX, a, f) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \begin{cases} \text{With } x = a - \frac{f}{2} \sqrt{\frac{-\ln(v)}{\ln(2)}} \text{ for } z \leq a \\ \text{and } x = a + \frac{f}{2} \sqrt{\frac{-\ln(v)}{\ln(2)}} \text{ for } z > a \\ x \quad \text{for } x_MIN \leq x \leq x_MAX \\ x_MIN \text{ for } x < x_MIN \\ x_MAX \text{ for } x > x_MAX \end{cases}$$

Multidimensionally bound categories

It is easy to specify multidimensionally bound categories by replacing the arguments of the validity functions with other functions, as the following examples illustrate for two dimensions:

Fig. 5: Category "Close to point ..."	$e_ESTIMATION(\sqrt{(x-1)^2+(y-1)^2}, 0, 0.4)$
Fig. 6: Category "At about a distance of 0.5 from point ..."	$e_ESTIMATION(\sqrt{(x-1)^2+(y-1)^2}, 0.5, 0.4)$
Fig. 7: Category "Approximately beyond ..."	$e_LIMITATION(x^2, y-1, 0.2)$

Fig. 5: Category "Close to point ..."

Fig. 6: Category "At about a distance of 0.5 from point ..."

Fig. 7: Category "Approximately beyond ..."

The paradigm of circumstantial evidence

The *paradigm of circumstantial evidence* illustrates the basic functionality of empirical logic reasoning. First, the notion *circumstantial evidence* must not be understood exactly in the way it is defined by jurisprudence. This concept, interpreted quite innocently, describes a method to derive factually true propositions from pieces of circumstantial evidence. *Indications* are facts which let the truth of an assumption (hypothesis) appear to be valid (evident) according to rules of experience (Fig. 8). Formally, a hypothesis will be expressed by one of the category notions explained above. The pieces of circumstantial evidence (trusted facts) collected as *indication series* are also described using the available forms of expressions for empirical logic categories. Indications confirm (*validate*) a hypothesis with variable weight as *pro-indications* or rather refute it (*invalidate*) as *contra-indications*. The empirical logic language takes this into account by means of the EL *weighting operator e_WEIGHT*.

Fig. 8: The paradigm of circumstantial evidence

Rules of experience, which interpret the existence of indications, provide evidence of the validity or invalidity of the hypothesis(es). At the beginning of this phase of enquiry, each category that represents a hypothesis will always be assigned the validity value *unknown* ($e_UNKNOWN()$). The computerized empirical logic provides both logical operators that let you formalize the premise of a rule of experience, as well as EL operators $e_VALIDATE$ and $e_INVALIDATE$ being used to determine the rule conclusion. Contradictory or rather

competing rules are clearly permitted and not at all an exception. Recursively iterating the rules imitates the example of the human way of thinking, which can be characterized by the term *weighing up*. Usually, the validity of a hypothesis will gradually approach a *converging value*. Ideally, the validity values of all categories involved in the given problem will finally assume a consistent and unopposed state of equilibrium.

Validating and invalidating a hypothesis

The key instruments of empirical logic reasoning comprise firstly the EL operator $e_VALIDATE$, which serves to confirm a hypothesis in terms of an affirmative validity assessment of its respective category, and secondly the EL operator $e_INVALIDATE$, which serves to refute it in terms of a negative validity assessment of its describing category.

Fig. 9: The validation operator $e_VALIDATE$

Fig. 10: The invalidation operator $e_INVALIDATE$

The function $e_VALIDATE: \mathbb{V}^{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}^n$ can be called with the following instruction syntax:

$$e_VALIDATE(p, h_1, \dots, h_n)$$

The arguments have the following meaning:

- p : Premise of the rule of experience with $p \in \mathbb{V}$.
- h_1, \dots, h_n : From 1 to n hypotheses with $h_i \in \mathbb{V}$ for $i = 1 \dots n$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$

The result of calling $e_VALIDATE$ is:

- c_1, \dots, c_n : From 1 to n conclusions with $c_i \in \mathbb{V}$ for $i = 1 \dots n$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$e_VALIDATE$ has this meaning:

<p>The premise is satisfied: $p \in \mathbb{V}_+$</p>	<p>The previous validity assessment of the hypothesis(es) will be validated (affirmed). In order to determine the next validity value of each conclusion c_i, there must exist a monotonously increasing and continuously differentiable function $f_{validate}$ with the following properties:</p> <p>$f_{validate}: \mathbb{V}_+ \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$, such that for each $i = 1 \dots n$:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) $c_i = f_{validate}(p, h_i) \geq h_i$ 2) $f_{validate}(p_1, f_{validate}(p_2, h_i)) = f_{validate}(p_2, f_{validate}(p_1, h_i))$ 3) $\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow e_UNKNOWN() \\ p > e_UNKNOWN()}} f_{validate}(p, h_i) = h_i$
<p>The premise is violated: $p \in \mathbb{V}_-$</p>	<p>The previous validity assessment of the hypothesis(es) will be kept:</p> <p>$c_i = h_i$ for each $i = 1 \dots n$</p>

The third property that is postulated for the implementation function $f_{validate}$ ensures that, from the user's perspective, the function of the EL operator $e_VALIDATE$ exhibits an overall continuity. That is, when the *activation threshold* has been reached with $p \geq e_UNKNOWN()$, the validity value(s) of the hypothesis(es) will

change, but gradually and without leaps. **Fig. 9** displays a graphical view of the EL operator $e_VALIDATE$ with a suitable implementation function.

The function of the corresponding invalidation operator $e_INVALIDATE: \mathbb{V}^{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}^n$ has this call instruction syntax:

$$e_INVALIDATE(p, h_1, \dots, h_n)$$

The arguments have the following meaning:

- p : Premise of the rule of experience with $p \in \mathbb{V}$.
 h_1, \dots, h_n : From 1 to n hypotheses with $h_i \in \mathbb{V}$ for $i = 1 \dots n$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$

The result of calling $e_INVALIDATE$ is:

- c_1, \dots, c_n : From 1 to n conclusions with $c_i \in \mathbb{V}$ for $i = 1 \dots n$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$e_INVALIDATE$ has this meaning:

<p>The premise is satisfied: $p \in \mathbb{V}_+$</p>	<p>The previous validity assessment of the hypothesis(es) will be invalidated (refuted). In order to determine the next validity value of each conclusion c_i, there must exist a monotonously decreasing and continuously differentiable function $f_{invalidate}$ with the following properties:</p> <p>$f_{invalidate}: \mathbb{V}_+ \times \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$, such that for each $i = 1 \dots n$:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) $c_i = f_{invalidate}(p, h_i) \leq h_i$ 2) $f_{invalidate}(p_1, f_{invalidate}(p_2, h_i)) = f_{invalidate}(p_2, f_{invalidate}(p_1, h_i))$ 3) $\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow e_UNKNOWN() \\ p > e_UNKNOWN()}} f_{invalidate}(p, h_i) = h_i$
<p>The premise is violated: $p \in \mathbb{V}_-$</p>	<p>The previous validity assessment of the hypothesis(es) will be kept:</p> <p>$c_i = h_i$ for each $i = 1 \dots n$</p>

As for the validation operator $e_VALIDATE$, the third property that is postulated for the implementation function $f_{invalidate}$ ensures again that, from the user's perspective, the function of the EL operator $e_INVALIDATE$ exhibits an overall continuity. **Fig. 10** displays a graphical view of a suitable implementation of the invalidation operator. Please note that its displayed functional surface can obviously be turned into the graph of the validation operator depicted in **Fig. 9** by a 180° rotation around the p-axis. Given the existence of a negation operator e_NOT , this suggests the following dual relations between $e_VALIDATE$ and $e_INVALIDATE$:

$$e_VALIDATE(p, h) = e_NOT(e_INVALIDATE(p, e_NOT(h)))$$

$$e_INVALIDATE(p, h) = e_NOT(e_VALIDATE(p, e_NOT(h)))$$

This means that the same type of relations must hold for the implementation functions $f_{validate}$ and $f_{invalidate}$ as well.

How to implement the validation and invalidation operator

The following explanation will show that some functions taken from the family of T- and S-norms are convenient to implement the EL operators $e_VALIDATE$ and $e_INVALIDATE$. T- and S-norms represent binary operations

$$T: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

$$S: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

which must have the following properties (Böhme, 1993, pp. 43 - 60), (Zimmermann, 1991, pp. 30 - 36), (Bronstein, et al., 2005, 2006, pp. 379 - 381):

- (1) 1 (for T) and 0 (for S) act as *identity elements*, such that: $T(1, x) = x$ and $S(0, x) = x$
- (2) T, S are *commutative*: $T(x, y) = T(y, x)$ and $S(x, y) = S(y, x)$
- (3) T, S are *associative*: $T(T(x, y), z) = T(x, T(y, z))$ and $S(S(x, y), z) = S(x, S(y, z))$

$$(4) \text{ T, S are monotonously increasing: } x \leq z \wedge y \leq w \Rightarrow \begin{cases} T(x, y) \leq T(z, w) \\ S(x, y) \leq S(z, w) \end{cases}$$

Theorem 1:

Continuously differentiable S-norms are suited to implement the EL operator $e_VALIDATE$ for arguments $p \in \mathbb{V}_+$ if they are normalized onto the validity interval $[0, 1]$.

Proof:

Step 1: Show that $f_{validate}(p, h_i) \geq h_i$

Define for $\mathbb{V} = [0, 1]$ and $p \in \mathbb{V}_+ = (0.5, 1]$:

$$p_{reduced} := p - e_TRUE() + e_UNKNOWN() = p - 1 + 0.5 = p - 0.5$$

Choose the following implementation function:

$$f_{validate}(p, h_i) := S(p_{reduced}, h_i) = S(p - 0.5, h_i)$$

Using axiom (4) of the S-norms (*monotonous increase*), define the following settings:

$$\begin{aligned} x &:= 0 \\ y &:= h_i \\ z &:= p_{reduced} = p - 0.5 \\ w &:= h_i \end{aligned}$$

The antecedent of the implication $x \leq z \wedge y \leq w \Rightarrow S(x, y) \leq S(z, w)$ then becomes:

$$0 \leq p - 0.5 \wedge h_i \leq h_i$$

For $\mathbb{V} = [0, 1]$ and $p \in \mathbb{V}_+ = (0.5, 1]$ this proposition is true.

The conclusion of the implication therefore yields:

$$S(0, h_i) \leq S(p_{reduced}, h_i)$$

Finally, from axiom (1) of the S-norms (0 is an *identity element*) follows the truth of the assertion:

$$S(p_{reduced}, h_i) \geq h_i$$

Step 2: Show that $f_{validate}(p_1, f_{validate}(p_2, h_i)) = f_{validate}(p_2, f_{validate}(p_1, h_i))$

With the implementation function chosen above, this corresponds to:

$$S(p_1 - 0.5, S(p_2 - 0.5, h_i)) = S(p_2 - 0.5, S(p_1 - 0.5, h_i))$$

With $i \in \{1, 2\}$ use the following abbreviation:

$$p_i^r := p_i - 0.5$$

Using the axioms (2) and (3) of the S-norms (i.e. *commutative* and *associative law*) the assertion becomes proofed:

$$S(p_1^r, S(p_2^r, h_i)) \stackrel{\text{Axiom (2)}}{\Leftrightarrow} S(p_1^r, S(h_i, p_2^r)) \stackrel{\text{Axiom (3)}}{\Leftrightarrow} S(S(p_1^r, h_i), p_2^r) \stackrel{\text{Axiom (2)}}{\Leftrightarrow} S(p_2^r, S(p_1^r, h_i))$$

Step 3: Show that $\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow e_UNKNOWN() \\ p > e_UNKNOWN()}} f_{validate}(p, h_i) = h_i$

Using the implementation function chosen above for the validity interval $\mathbb{V} = [0, 1]$, this equals:

$$\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow 0.5 \\ p > 0.5}} S(p - 0.5, h_i) = h_i$$

Using axiom (1) of the S-norms (0 is an *identity element*), this proves the assertion:

$$\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow 0.5 \\ p > 0.5}} S(p - 0.5, h_i) = S(0, h_i) = h_i$$

End of proof

Theorem 2:

Continuously differentiable T-norms are suited to implement the EL operator $e_INVALIDATE$ for arguments $p \in \mathbb{V}_+$ if they are normalized onto the validity interval $[0, 1]$.

Proof:

Step 1: Show that $f_{invalidate}(p, h_i) \leq h_i$

As for theorem 1, define again for $\mathbb{V} = [0, 1]$ and $p \in \mathbb{V}_+ = (0.5, 1]$:

$$p_{reduced} := p - e_TRUE() + e_UNKNOWN() = p - 1 + 0.5 = p - 0.5$$

Choose now a different implementation function:

$$f_{invalidate}(p, h_i) := T(1 - p_{reduced}, h_i) = T(1.5 - p, h_i)$$

This time, when using axiom (4) of the T-norms (*monotonous increase*), specify the following settings:

$$x := 1 - p_{reduced} = 1.5 - p$$

$$y := h_i$$

$$z := 1$$

$$w := h_i$$

Now, the antecedent of the implication $x \leq z \wedge y \leq w \Rightarrow T(x, y) \leq T(z, w)$ becomes:

$$1.5 - p \leq 1 \wedge h_i \leq h_i$$

This proposition is true again for $p \in \mathbb{V}_+ = (0.5, 1]$.

The conclusion of the implication then becomes:

$$T(1 - p_{reduced}, h_i) \leq T(1, h_i)$$

Again, axiom (1) of the T-norms (1 is an *identity element*) ensures the truth of the assertion:

$$T(1 - p_{reduced}, h_i) \leq h_i$$

Step 2: Show that $f_{invalidate}(p_1, f_{invalidate}(p_2, h_i)) = f_{invalidate}(p_2, f_{invalidate}(p_1, h_i))$

With the implementation function chosen above, this corresponds to:

$$T(1.5 - p_1, T(1.5 - p_2, h_i)) = T(1.5 - p_2, T(1.5 - p_1, h_i))$$

With $i \in \{1, 2\}$ use the following abbreviation:

$$p_i^r := 1.5 - p_i$$

Using again the axioms (2) and (3) of the T-norms (i.e. *commutative* and *associative law*) the assertion becomes true:

$$T(p_1^r, T(p_2^r, h_i)) \stackrel{\text{Axiom (2)}}{\Leftrightarrow} T(p_1^r, T(h_i, p_2^r)) \stackrel{\text{Axiom (3)}}{\Leftrightarrow} T(T(p_1^r, h_i), p_2^r) \stackrel{\text{Axiom (2)}}{\Leftrightarrow} T(p_2^r, T(p_1^r, h_i))$$

Step 3: Show that $\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow e_UNKNOWN() \\ p > e_UNKNOWN()}} f_{invalidate}(p, h_i) = h_i$

With the implementation function selected above for the validity interval $\mathbb{V} = [0, 1]$, this equals:

$$\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow 0.5 \\ p > 0.5}} T(1.5 - p, h_i) = h_i$$

Using axiom (1) of the T-norms (1 is an *identity element*), this proves the assertion:

$$\lim_{\substack{p \rightarrow 0.5 \\ p > 0.5}} T(1.5 - p, h_i) = T(1, h_i) = h_i$$

End of proof

The explanations given above will be incomplete without proving that the implementation functions found fulfill the claimed dual relations between the EL operators $e_VALIDATE$ and $e_INVALIDATE$:

Theorem 3:

Continuously differentiable implementation functions

$$f_{\text{validate}}(p, h_i) := S(p_{\text{reduced}}, h_i) = S(p - 0.5, h_i)$$

$$f_{\text{invalidate}}(p, h_i) := T(1 - p_{\text{reduced}}, h_i) = T(1.5 - p, h_i)$$

using dual T- and S-norms fulfill the corresponding duality relations within the validity interval $[0, 1]$:

$$f_{\text{validate}}(p, h_i) = e_{\text{NOT}}(f_{\text{invalidate}}(p, e_{\text{NOT}}(h_i)))$$

$$f_{\text{invalidate}}(p, h_i) = e_{\text{NOT}}(f_{\text{validate}}(p, e_{\text{NOT}}(h_i)))$$

Proof:

After inserting the implementation functions, the first of the asserted relations looks like this:

$$S(p - 0.5, h_i) = 1 - T(1.5 - p, 1 - h_i)$$

or with an equivalent notation by setting $p^* := p - 0.5$:

$$S(p^*, h_i) = 1 - T(1 - p^*, 1 - h_i)$$

This statement is true, because with the one's complement (negation in the validity interval $[0, 1]$) dual T- and S-Norms comply with *De Morgan's laws* (Böhme, 1993, p. 54), (Michels, et al., 2002, pp. 16-17).

After inserting the implementation functions, the second asserted dual relation turns out to be:

$$T(1.5 - p, h_i) = 1 - S(p - 0.5, 1 - h_i)$$

or with setting $p^+ := 1.5 - p$:

$$T(p^+, h_i) = 1 - S(1 - p^+, 1 - h_i)$$

which is true as well, according to *De Morgan's laws*.

End of proof

In order to use the EL operators e_{VALIDATE} and $e_{\text{INVALIDATE}}$ inside the validity interval $[-1, 1]$, the considered T- and S-norms need to complete their implementations by respective mappings between the two available validity intervals:

$$N: [-1, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1] \text{ with } N(v) = \frac{1}{2}(v + 1)$$

$$R: [0, 1] \rightarrow [-1, 1] \text{ with } R(v) = 2v - 1$$

As an example, the graphical views of **Fig. 9** and **Fig. 10** illustrate the following implementations (**Tab. 1**) using T- and S-norms, which have proven to be efficient in several application examples.

EL operator	Implementation function	
e_{VALIDATE}	Einstein sum (S-norm)	$f_{\text{validate}}(p, h_i) = \frac{p_{\text{reduced}} + h_i}{1 + p_{\text{reduced}} \cdot h_i}$ with $p_{\text{reduced}} := p - 0.5$
$e_{\text{INVALIDATE}}$	Einstein product (T-norm)	$f_{\text{invalidate}}(p, h_i) = \frac{p_{\text{reduced}} \cdot h_i}{1 + (1 - p_{\text{reduced}}) \cdot (1 - h_i)}$ with $p_{\text{reduced}} := 1.5 - p$

Tab. 1: Implementing e_{VALIDATE} ($e_{\text{INVALIDATE}}$) using the Einstein sum (product)

Other candidates for implementing the validation (invalidation) operator, such as for instance the *algebraic sum (product)*, the *algebraic S-quotient (T-quotient)* by Hamacher, the *Hamacher S-norm (T-norm)*, the *Frank S-norm (T-norm)*, or the *Dombi S-norm (T-norm)*, have turned out to be less efficient after careful testing (Bronstein, et al., 2005, 2006, p. 381).

Logical EL operators

Logical EL operators provide the logical interconnections between partial statements of the premise p when calling $e_VALIDATE(p, h_1, \dots, h_n)$ or $e_INVALIDATE(p, h_1, \dots, h_n)$. They all share the following syntactic form:

$$e_Operatorname(v_1, \dots, v_n) \text{ with } v_i \in \mathbb{V} \text{ and } i = 1 \dots n \ (n \in \mathbb{N})$$

Fig. 11: e_AND

Fig. 12: e_OR

Fig. 13: e_XOR

That is, the number of arguments is variable and not constrained. The result must not depend on the order of the arguments. Except for the negation operator e_NOT , every logical EL operator takes at least two arguments.

Tab. 2 displays a summary of the available logical operators.

Logical EL operator	Meaning
$e_NOT: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}^n$	Negation of the arguments v_1, \dots, v_n : 1) $\mathbb{V} = [-1, 1]: e_NOT(v_1, \dots, v_n) = -v_1, \dots, -v_n$ 2) $\mathbb{V} = [0, 1]: e_NOT(v_1, \dots, v_n) = 1 - v_1, \dots, 1 - v_n$
$e_AND: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Conjunctive connection (C-norm) of the arguments v_1, \dots, v_n
$e_OR: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Disjunctive connection (D-norm) of the arguments v_1, \dots, v_n
$e_XOR: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	With $v_j := \max(v_1, \dots, v_n)$ equivalent to: $e_AND(e_NOT(v_1), \dots, e_NOT(v_{j-1}), v_j, e_NOT(v_{j+1}), \dots, e_NOT(v_n))$
$e_IF_POSSIBLE_ALL_OF: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Equivalent to e_AND .
$e_SEVERAL_OF: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Equivalent to e_OR .
$e_ONLY_ONE_OF: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Equivalent to e_XOR .
$e_NECESSARILY_ALL_OF: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Equal to $\min(v_1, \dots, v_n)$, which may be interpreted as the universal quantifier \forall .
$e_AT_LEAST_ONE_OF: \mathbb{V}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$	Equal to $\max(v_1, \dots, v_n)$, which may be interpreted as the existential quantifier \in .

Tab. 2: Summary of available logical EL operators

C- and D-norms

The properties listed in Tab. 3 define the architecture of the fundamental logical operators e_AND and e_OR . If the EL operator e_AND (e_OR) meets the axioms 1 to 5, they are called *C-norms* (*D-norms*), where the “C” (“D”) refers to a *conjunction* (*disjunction*). If the EL operator e_AND (e_OR) also meets axiom 6, then its architecture represents a *neutral C-norm* (*neutral D-norm*).

Axiom 1 (*continuous differentiability*) considers that the mental process of estimating the evidence of a hypothesis, the weighing up between competing decisions, and other pondering activities does not occur in leaps and bounds.

Axiom 2 and **3** (*commutativity, monotonous growth*) correspond to similar axioms (2) and (4) of the T- and S-norms.

Axiom 4 (*characteristic values*) has a certain correspondence to axiom (1) of the T- and S-norms (*identity elements*), because it follows from this one. But the reverse conclusion does not hold: Neither the validity value $e_TRUE()$ is an identity element of the C-norms nor $e_FALSE()$ an identity element of the D-norms.

Axiom 5 (*De Morgan's laws*) expresses the logical duality relation between C- and D-norms: Using the negation operator, any C-norm can be turned into a well-defined D-norm and vice versa. Note that the axioms of the T- and S-norms do not involve De Morgan's laws, although they apply there when matching functions with a dual relationship are chosen (e.g. the minimum operator as a T-norm and the maximum operator as an S-norm). For the C- and D-norms, axiom 5 serves the purpose of preventing the combination of logically incompatible functions.

Axiom 6 (*neutrality*) postulates that a logical combination of statements cannot be a source of (previously unavailable) information. This means that the result of a logical combination must not feign a higher degree of certainty than can be derived from the certainties of the partial statements.

<p>1) Continuous differentiability</p> <p>With $I := [false, true] \subset \mathbb{R}$ such that $true := 1$ and $false := \begin{cases} -1 \text{ for } \forall \\ 0 \text{ for } \vee \end{cases} \in [-1, 1]$</p> <p>the following functions are continuously differentiable:</p> <p>Conjunction: $C: I \times \dots \times I \rightarrow I$ with $y = C(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ (alternative notation: $y = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n x_i$)</p> <p>Disjunction: $D: I \times \dots \times I \rightarrow I$ with $y = D(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ (alternative notation: $y = \bigvee_{i=1}^n x_i$)</p>
<p>2) Commutativity</p> <p>$C(x_1, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_j, \dots, x_n) = C(x_1, \dots, x_j, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n)$ and $D(x_1, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_j, \dots, x_n) = D(x_1, \dots, x_j, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n)$</p>
<p>3) Monotonous growth</p> <p>$\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}: x_i \leq z_i \Rightarrow C(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq C(z_1, \dots, z_n)$ and $D(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq D(z_1, \dots, z_n)$</p>
<p>4) Characteristic values</p> <p>Conjunction: $\begin{cases} \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}: x_i = true \Rightarrow C(x_1, \dots, x_n) = true \\ \exists i \in \{1, \dots, n\}: x_i = false \Rightarrow C(x_1, \dots, x_n) = false \end{cases}$</p> <p>Disjunction: $\begin{cases} \exists i \in \{1, \dots, n\}: x_i = true \Rightarrow D(x_1, \dots, x_n) = true \\ \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\}: x_i = false \Rightarrow D(x_1, \dots, x_n) = false \end{cases}$</p>
<p>5) De Morgan's laws</p> <p>With $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $\neg x_i := \begin{cases} -x_i & \text{for } \forall \in [-1, 1] \\ 1 - x_i & \text{for } \forall \in [0, 1] \end{cases}$ applies</p> <p>$\neg C(x_1, \dots, x_n) = D(\neg x_1, \dots, \neg x_n)$ and $\neg D(x_1, \dots, x_n) = C(\neg x_1, \dots, \neg x_n)$</p>
<p>6) Neutrality</p> <p>$\min\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \leq C(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq \max\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and $\min\{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \leq D(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq \max\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$</p>

Tab. 3: C- and D-norms

Please note that deliberately, there is no axiom for associativity, because this would exclude some functions with useful properties from choices for implementing the EL operators e_AND and e_OR . For example, the graphical views of EL operators e_AND (**Fig. 11**) and e_OR (**Fig. 12**) are the result of an implementation with the generalized mean using the weighting factor $e_P = -0.5$, which turns out to meet the requirements of neutral C- and D-norms (Arens, et al., 2015, p. 1375):

EL operator	Implementation function for validity interval [0, 1]	
$y = e_AND(x_1, \dots, x_n)$	Generalized mean (C-norm)	$y = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^{e_P} \right)^{\frac{1}{e_P}}$
$y = e_OR(x_1, \dots, x_n)$	Generalized mean (D-norm)	$y = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - x_i)^{e_P} \right)^{\frac{1}{e_P}}$

Tab. 4: Implementing e_AND (e_OR) using the generalized mean as C-norm (D-norm)

Extensive testing has proven that in addition to the above-mentioned implementation options for $e_VALIDATE$ and $e_INVALIDATE$, you can also implement the conjunctive (disjunctive) operator e_AND (e_OR) with less favorable results using the *geometric* and *harmonic mean* and the *Gamma operator* by Zimmermann and Zysno (Zimmermann & Zysno, 1980).

Logical operators with modulated arguments

Often, practical decision-making circumstances require dynamic judgement of the relevance (validity values) of pro- and contra-indications for a given hypothesis. For example, in the “just-in-time”-manufacturing industry or logistics, it is important to know to what extent parts from suppliers meet the category “The delivery is on time”. The authors H. Rekersbrink, B. Ludwig and B. Scholz-Reiter rightly point out that in transport logistics, a compensatory effect between certain criteria, such as for instance “deadline compliance” and “profitability”, loses importance as soon as a consignment threatens to fall into the category “delivery is in default” (Rekersbrink, et al., 2007). At this moment, it therefore becomes important to give priority to the goal “deadline compliance” by a modulation of the category “delivery is in default” without overriding the previously defined weighting structure of the logistical target criteria. In empirical logic, this is possible by adapting the arguments of the EL operators using a special syntax. If, for example, in the expression $e_AND(v_1, \dots, v_i, \dots, v_n)$ the validity value v_i is to be changed with the modulation parameter $m \in [-1, 1]$, the following notation is allowed:

$$e_AND(v_1, \dots, [v_i, m], \dots, v_n)$$

Using the abbreviation $\mathbb{V}^* := \{e_UNKNOWN(), e_TRUE(), e_FALSE()\}$, the notation “[v, m]” has the meaning of a monotonously increasing function $e_MODULATE: \mathbb{V} \times [-1, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$ with the following properties:

- (1) $m = 0 \Rightarrow e_MODULATE(v, m) = v$ (Value of argument v remains unchanged)
- (2) $m \in [-1, 1], v \in \mathbb{V}^* \Rightarrow e_MODULATE(v, m) = v$ (Value of argument v remains unchanged)
- (3) $m > 0, v \in V_+ \Rightarrow e_MODULATE(v, m) > v$ (Positive trend of argument v is strengthened)
- (4) $m > 0, v \in V_- \Rightarrow e_MODULATE(v, m) \leq v$ (Negative trend of argument v is strengthened)
- (5) $m < 0, v \in V_+ \Rightarrow e_MODULATE(v, m) < v$ (Positive trend of argument v is attenuated)
- (6) $m < 0, v \in V_- \Rightarrow e_MODULATE(v, m) \geq v$ (Negative trend of argument v is attenuated)

Such a function can be generated, for example, from the linear combination of two oppositely directed sigmoid functions (cf. Fig. 15).

The graphs in Fig. 14 show the effect of modulating the arguments on the result of a logical connection using the EL operator e_AND .

Fig. 14: Logical operator e_AND with and without modulated arguments

As an example, Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 illustrate the difference between *weighting* and *modulating* the category “delivery is in default”. Figuratively speaking, the modulation of EL operator arguments changes the “focus” on the respective category, so that it appears “sharp” to different degrees. In other words: Validity modulation is a method to draw attention on the categories of relevant decision criteria in a critical situation.

Fig. 15: Meaning of a modulated validity $[v, m] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e_MODULATE(v, m)$

Fig. 16: Weighting a category

Fig. 17: Modulating a category

The decision operator e_DECIDE

The *decision operator* $e_DECIDE: \mathbb{V}_+ \times \mathbb{V}_- \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$ can be used to net the results from applying the validation operator $e_VALIDATE$ to pro-indications of a hypothesis and subsequently applying the invalidation operator $e_INVALIDATE$ to contra-indications of the same hypothesis. This is important to know, as you cannot process a series of pro- and contra-indications in a mixed order due to the following inequality:

$$\exists p, k, h \in \mathbb{V}: e_INVALIDATE(k, e_VALIDATE(p, h)) \neq e_VALIDATE(p, e_INVALIDATE(k, h))$$

The variables of the EL expression $r = e_DECIDE(v, i)$ have the following meaning:

- v : Total validity value of the pro-indications with $v \in \mathbb{V}_+$
- i : Total validity value of the contra-indications with $i \in \mathbb{V}_-$
- r : Resulting validity value with $r = v + i - e_UNKNOWN()$ and $r \in \mathbb{V}$

4 The book sorting problem (application example)

The following application example refers to the assignment problem described by David W. Tank und John J. Hopfield as a *book sorting problem* in their 1987 paper “*Collective Computation in Neuronlike Circuits*” (Tank & Hopfield, 1987), (Tank & Hopfield, 1988):

In a library, the student assistants Sarah, Rita, Hans, Karin, Klaus and Jan are supposed to sort books from the specialist fields geology, physics, chemistry, history, poetry and art into the shelves as fast as possible. Each student has knowledge of these subjects, but to varying degrees, such that Rita can sort six books per minute in geology, four books per minute in physics and so on, while Hans manages one book per minute in geology, eight per minute in physics and so on. How should the tasks be distributed so that all the work is done as quickly as possible? The optimal task assignment among $6! = 720$ different solutions with a total sorting speed of 44 books per minute is indicated in **Tab. 5** by highlighting the respective sorting rates.

		specialist fields					
		geology	physics	chemistry	history	poetry	art
library assistants	Sarah	10	5	4	6	5	1
	Rita	6	4	9	7	3	2
	Hans	1	8	3	6	4	6
	Karin	5	3	7	2	1	4
	Klaus	3	2	5	6	8	7
	Jan	7	6	4	1	3	2

Tab. 5: Book sorting rates of the library helpers [books per minute]

In order to solve this assignment problem in an analogous neuronlike manner, as David W. Tank und John J. Hopfield have shown with their electronic circuit, but this time using empirical logic, the first step requires us to identify the categories involved:

Assignment preferences and decisions

An *assignment preference* is a bound category and reads “high sorting velocity” for the example of the book sorting problem. It has the sorting rates of the library assistants compiled in **Tab. 5** as its reference magnitude. The threshold function $e_THRESHOLD(x, t, f)$ can be used to describe it with suitable parameters $t = 5.5$ (*validity threshold*) and $f = 0.7$ (*fuzziness*) (**Fig. 18**). Moreover, this category suggests a relation “Library assistant i can sort books from the field j with high velocity”. **Fig. 19** displays its validity values as a two-dimensional bar chart.

Other than the assignment preferences, an assignment decision is a free category, because it is not bound to any scalable reference magnitude. In its entirety, the decisions which library assistant should work on which task represents another relation $D = (d_{ij})_{mn} \in \mathbb{V}^{m \times n}$, suggesting a matrix display format, too.

During the solution search, it dynamically describes the validities of the respective assignment decisions as a set of hypotheses. At first, all assignment decisions have the validity value $e_UNKNOWN()$ as an initial state. These values gradually change until a consistent distribution of sorting tasks is found, such that each library assistant sorts at most one specialist field and, vice versa, each field will be sorted by at most one assistant. **Fig. 20** shows how the relation D moves on from the initial state via a sequence of intermediate states to a permissible final state. At the same time, this coincides with the optimal solution to the book sorting problem.

Fig. 18: Category "high sorting velocity"

Fig. 19: Relation "Library assistant i can sort books from the field j with high velocity"

Fig. 20: Validity of assignment decisions during the solution search

Determining the solution with empirical logic rules

Validation rule:	<p>IF library assistant i meets the assignment preferences for specialist field j</p> <p>AND there is <u>neither</u> a decision for the assignment of field j to another assistant k <u>nor</u> for the assignment of the assistant i to another field l,</p> <p>THEN the decision that assistant i receives the sorting task for field j is valid.</p>
Invalidation rule:	<p>IF library assistant i does <u>not</u> meet the assignment preferences for specialist field j</p> <p>OR there is a decision for the assignment of field j to another assistant k <u>or</u> for the assignment of the assistant i to another field l,</p> <p>THEN the decision that assistant i receives the sorting task for field j is <u>not</u> valid.</p>

Tab. 6: Empirical logic rules of the book sorting problem

According to what was said earlier about circumstantial evidence as a paradigm of empirical logic reasoning, each individual assignment decision between library assistant and specialist field represents a hypothesis the validity of which must be proven or refuted based on the assignment preferences and the agreed restrictions. For the assignment problem, shown by the example of the book sorting task, two simple rules are sufficient (**Tab. 6**).

The formalization of the rules with the available EL operators looks like this for all library assistants $i = 1 \dots m$ and all specialist fields $j = 1 \dots n$ with $i \notin \{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_{m-1}\}$ and $j \notin \{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_{n-1}\}$:

Validation rule: $d_{ij}^{t+1} := e_VALIDATE(e_AND(p_{ij}, e_NOT(d_{k_1j}^t, d_{k_2j}^t, \dots, d_{il_1}^t, d_{il_2}^t, \dots))), d_{ij}^t)$

Invalidation rule: $d_{ij}^{t+1} := e_INVALIDATE(e_OR(e_NOT(p_{ij}), d_{k_1j}^t, d_{k_2j}^t, \dots, d_{il_1}^t, d_{il_2}^t, \dots), d_{ij}^t)$

Note that the variables p_{ij} denote the validity values of the above-described assignment preferences, and d_{ij}^t and d_{ij}^{t+1} the validity values of the assignment decisions at the times before and after execution of a rule during iteration phase $t + 1$. The entirety of validation and invalidation rules forms a network structure of collectively interacting assignment decisions. However, some precautions must be taken in the implementation of the rules, so that the principle of collective interaction is correctly reflected:

- 1) It is allowed and useful to apply first all validation rules and then all invalidation rules for the assignment decisions d_{ij} in an iteration phase t .
- 2) However, it is not allowed to apply the rules on the same matrix data structure $(d_{ij})_{mn}$. Otherwise, the new validity values of the assignment decisions would depend on the execution order and would be distorted. Therefore, it is necessary to explicitly provide a second matrix data structure $(d_{ij}^{t+1})_{m,n}$ which takes the results calculated from iteration phase t . In the iteration step $t + 1$, the two data structures exchange their role, which is also referred to as *swapping* in software terminology.

Up to this point, the focus has been on the structure and the mutual relationships between the empirical rules for solving the assignment problem. Regarding the semantics of the rules, it should be mentioned that they do not have to consider any criteria, such as opportunity costs (shadow prices), which indicate whether a solution has reached its optimum. In contrast to an algorithmic method, the empirical rules are limited to the required properties of the solution itself, which is much easier to determine. Nevertheless, the rules allow finding an optimal or at least good suboptimal solution with high reliability. A test study, consisting of 532 scenarios with 300 randomly selected test cases each, proved that the book sorting problem, with six library assistants and specialist fields each, can be solved with a mean hit accuracy of approximately 96% (0.9628). This result was achieved with an average number of rule iterations between 21 and 22, using the EL operator implementations listed in **Tab. 1** and **Tab. 4**. At a confidence level of 95%, the corresponding confidence interval turned out to be (Schira, 2021, p. 454):

$$CI(0.9628, 0.95) = [94.14\%, 98.42\%]$$

5 Other possible empirical logic applications

In addition to the above-described book sorting problem, the empirical logic could be successfully tested using the following application examples:

Sales potential analysis for fashionable retail items

Forecasting sales of apparel items in the retail sector is particularly difficult. Rapidly changing fashion trends on the provider side act as erratic events on buyer demand. A time series analysis of turnover is not a reliable method for forecasting sales because the basic assumption that previous data reflect causal relationships which can be uncovered with the help of quantitative analysis is not valid in this case [cf. 11 (p. 244)]. However, a bad forecast either leads to excessive inventories, which must be reduced with costly discounts, or to stock shortages with correspondingly high lost profits. A particularly complex facet of the sales forecast is the distribution of the order quantities across the clothing sizes.

Fig. 21 indicates that this problem can be solved in the form of an expert system, in which the sales potential for the seasonal fashion collections is determined from the comparison of customer profiles and trend profiles using the specialist knowledge of a fashion expert, formulated with the expressive possibilities of empirical logic.

Fig. 21: Principle of sales potential analysis^{2,3}

Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP)

The *traveling salesman problem* belongs to the NP-hard combinatorial problems (Hopcroft & Ullman, 1988, p. 348). In addition to transport logistics, solutions also play an important role in construction and manufacturing technology, e.g. in chip design or in determining the optimal paths when drilling printed circuit boards in semiconductor production. A Maple prototype developed with empirical logic has shown that the problem can be solved with rules like those of the assignment problem. The measured hit reliability was about 80% (Fig. 22). The required computing time has the order of $T(n) \approx O(n^5)$ (Fig. 23).

Fig. 22: Results of testing the Traveling Salesman Problem

² Image source: „Sommerschlußverkauf eines Textilgeschäfts in Bonn (1991)“, German Federal Archives, B 145 Bild-F088826-0014 / Faßbender, Julia / CC-BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5473709>

³ Image source: „Défilé de mode au Nigeria“: Par Hycinth Iyereosa — Travail personnel, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=36898496>

Fig. 23: Measured and estimated TSP computer run times

Water level control of a reservoir

Fig. 24: Water level control of a reservoir

The task of the example is to control the water level of a reservoir with the help of a weir using a movable gate with flow passing underneath or above (gate, segment, roller, etc.). Since it should only be important to show the principle of a controller based on empirical logic, the task description is greatly simplified: It is assumed that the reservoir has the shape of a simple retention basin with vertical sheet piling all around, like a cofferdam, and a flat bottom. The aim is to keep the water level h , which represents the controlled variable of the process, at the setpoint h_s in the sense of a *fixed value control*. The disturbance variable of the controlled section is the inflowing water quantity q_e , which can deviate from the discharge quantity q_a adjusted via the opening width of the weir gate (Fig. 24).

Without getting into the formalization details with the help of empirical logic, it should be mentioned that this task was solved as a Maple prototype with two simple rules of the following meaning:

- (1) IF the water level is low OR the water level is falling THEN reduce the weir opening.
- (2) IF the water level is high OR the water level is climbing THEN expand the weir opening.

This is remarkable, considering that a Mamdani fuzzy controller developed for comparison purposes requires 49 rules for the same task. Fig. 25 shows the transient responses of the two controller types for a sampling frequency of one hour.

Fig. 25: Comparison of the disturbance step responses ($\Delta q_e/q_a = 30\%$)

Speed control of a DC motor

Fig. 26: Speed control of a DC motor⁴

The following example is taken from a German text book on control engineering (Föllinger, 2016). Among other sample applications, the book deals with the stability behavior of a DC motor speed control, using a PI and a PID controller (Fig. 26). For comparison purposes, the author designed and tested an empirical logic controller (EL controller) for the same system. As in the previous example of the weir example, only two similarly designed rules are required.

The graphs in Fig. 27 and Fig. 28 show that the EL stabilization of the DC motor achieved with the above-mentioned empirical logic rules need not fear comparison with a technically optimized PI or PID control system. Fig. 27 shows that the EL controller responds to a setpoint step change faster than the PI controller and a little slower than the PID controller. After a step change in the disturbance variable (Fig. 28), the controlled variable reaches the stationary state even faster with the EL controller than with the PID controller.

⁴ Image from: Föllinger, O.: Regelungstechnik. Einführung in die Methoden und ihre Anwendung. 12. Aufl. Berlin · Offenbach: VDE Verlag, 2016 (Reproduction with English translations of labels courtesy of VDE-Verlag)

Fig. 27: Comparison of setpoint step responses

Fig. 28: Comparison of disturbance step responses

6 Summary

The formal and computerized language called *empirical logic* was developed according to the method of bionics, taking as a model the cognitive information processing known in psychology as *system 1*. The architecture of the language, which belongs to the field of soft computing, is derived from experiments with electronic circuits based on neurobiological models, which were investigated by neuroscientists David Tank and John Hopfield as early as the 1980s. These indicate that evolution has brought about fast-acting chains of effects for the subconscious perception process that are similar to the signal processing of the biological nervous system that performs the process. Usage examples of empirical logic from the fields of business administration, operations research and control engineering, which have been prototyped with Maple, indicate a wide range of applications.

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Data Availability

The Maple prototypes and test results described in this article are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by the author.

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